

Changes in grain dry weight and water content of rice stressed at different stages after panicle emergence.^a

(d)	PE ^b before maximum WD ^c	Cultivar	Change in dry weight		Change in water content		Water loss and dry weight relationship	
			(mg/d)	<i>r</i>	(%/d)	<i>r</i>	slope	<i>r</i>
20-25	AUS257		1.8	0.97**	3.8	0.98**	-0.33	0.97**
15-19	AUS196		1.4	0.98**	5.5	0.99**	-0.27	0.92**
15-19	UPLRi-7		1.7	0.96**	2.5	0.99**	-0.43	0.95**
10-14	AUS257		0.8	0.88*	3.3	0.99**	-0.41	0.98**
10-14	IRAT104		2.4	0.98**	4.2	0.91**	-0.82	0.92**
5-9	IR43		1.1	0.98**	2.4	0.99**	-0.42	0.96**
0-4	UPLRi-7		1.7	0.99**	1.9	0.98**	-0.68	0.99**
0-4	UPLRi-7		1.7	0.98**	1.8	0.99**	-0.80	0.96**
SD			0.45		1.2		0.20	

a*, ** = Significant and highly significant, respectively, at the 5% level, ^bPE = panicle emergence. ^cWD = water deficit.

emergence period of 10-14 d before maximum water deficit, AUS257, a small-seeded cultivar, increased grain dry weight by 0.8 mg/d while IRAT104, a large-seeded cultivar, increased its

grain dry weight by 2.4 mg/d (see table).

Except for AUS257, water content was almost constant until 5-6 d after panicle emergence, after which it decreased almost linearly. At harvest,

grain water content ranged from 10 to 30% (see figure). Rice grain lost less water when panicle emergence was close to maximum water deficit (UPLRi-7 grain lost 1.8% water/d) than when panicles emerged between 15 and 19 d before maximum water deficit (grain lost 2.5% water/d). IRAT104 lost 4.2% water/d compared with AUS257, which lost only 3.3% water/d, even though their panicles emerged within the same period.

Grain water content and grain dry weight were negatively correlated (see table). The leveling off in dry weight was not accompanied by leveling off in water content because water loss continued for a few more days. These findings suggest that even if grain is fully mature, it continues to lose water even under water deficit. Results also suggest that a decrease in water loss in the grain was due to low water status during water deficit and not mainly to maturation. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

Kairala (Ptb49), a high-yielding rice variety with multiple resistance from Kerala, India

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Popular high-yielding rice varieties of Kerala—Jyothi, Pavizham, and Annapoorna—were crossed with highly adaptable IR36 in a breeding program to develop varieties with multiple resistance to pests. Single plants with desired attributes were selected from the segregating population.

KAU8754, a promising culture isolated from the cross IR36/Jyothi, showed high yield potential and moderate to high levels of resistance to leaf blast, neck blast, sheath blight, gall midge biotypes 1 and 4, and whitebacked planthopper. This elite line was released as Kairali (Ptb49) in 1993.

The variety was highly promising in station trials from 1987 to 1991, with a mean yield of 4.1 t/ha. In the 1991-92 kharif (dry) season, the variety yielded a

mean of 5.2 t/ha across 23 locations in the All India Coordinated Trials, indicating high adaptability to different soil and environmental conditions (see table). The mean yield of Kairali was 500 kg/ha higher than Ratna, the check variety.

Grain is long bold with red kernels. Milling and cooking qualities are excellent.

Performance of Kairali at different sites in India.

Location	Mean grain yield (t/ha)	
	Kairali	Ratna
Kerala	4.7	4.1
Tamil Nadu	5.4	5.5
Karnataka	4.7	4.1
Andhra Pradesh	4.6	4.0
Maharashtra	3.2	2.8
Haryana	6.8	6.3
Rajasthan	5.4	5.4
Punjab	5.0	4.3
Jammu and Kashmir	5.5	4.0
Mean ^a	5.2	4.7

^aMean of two seasons at 23 locations.

With a duration of 110-115 d, the variety is recommended for all three rice-growing seasons of Kerala (kharif, rabi [wet], and summer). ■

Zhefu No. 9, a new indica rice variety in central and eastern China

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Zhefu No.9, derived from cross 44-1086/IR50, was released in Apr 1993 for use as an early season (April to July) indica variety in the double-cropped area of central and eastern China.

Zhefu No. 9 is a short-duration, semidwarf indica rice. It is 80-85 cm tall and has 105-110 d growth duration. Average yield is about 6.6 t/ha under normal cultivation and maximum yield is 8.8 t/ha under high fertilization and good management, which was 8.1-18.7% and 4.3-20.1% more than the checks,

Table 1. Yield potential of Zhefu No. 9 in regional tests in eastern and central China, 1991.

Site	Average		Maximum	
	Yield (t/ha)	Increase over check (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Increase over check (%)
Hangzhou, Zhejiang	6.3	8.1 ^a	8.8	15.2 ^a
Ninbo, Zhejiang	6.9	10.4 ^a	8.1	4.3 ^a
Linhai, Zhejiang	5.8	7.7 ^a	7.7	10.2 ^a
Wuzhou, Jiangxi	6.8	10.5 ^a	7.7	12.6 ^a
Shangrao, Jiangxi	6.5	6.2 ^a	7.8	11.5 ^a
Changsha, Hunan	7.0	18.7 ^b	8.0	20.1 ^b
Yuyang, Hunan	7.1	10.2 ^b	8.6	18.3 ^b
Wuhan, Hubei	6.5	14.7 ^b	7.5	18.9 ^b

^aErjiufong. ^bZhefu No. 802.

Table 2. Morphoagronomic characters of Zhefu No. 9 at different sites in central and eastern China, 1992.

Character	Hangzhou, Zhejiang	Wuzhou, Jiangxi	Xiangtan, Hunan	Wuhan, Hubei
Plant height (cm)	81.0	74.5	85.0	88.0
Panicle length (cm)	18.3	18.1	19.4	21.0
Grains (no./panicle)	100.5	102.4	124.0	129.0
Fertility (%)	78.0	83.6	86.5	78.6
1,000 grain wt (g)	22.6	22.9	22.0	22.8

respectively (Table 1). It is highly resistant to rice blast under field conditions. (See Table 2 for morphoagronomic characters.)

It has medium grain and good cooking quality, with an amylose content of 23.1%. ■

Xin Guang S, a promising photoperiod/temperature-sensitive genic male sterile (P/TGMS) line for two-line system of hybrid rice breeding

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Seed set of bagged panicles of Xin Guang S grown in the phytotron, CNRRI, Fuyang, China. 1992.

Temperature ^a (°C)	Daylength ^b (h/d)	Plants observed (no.)	Seed set of bagged panicle (%)
30.1	15.0	15	0 ± 0
	14.0	15	0 ± 0
	12.5	15	0 ± 0
24.1	15.0	15	0.67 ± 1.44
	14.0	15	0.22 ± 0.58
	12.5	15	57.33 ± 10.75
23.1	15.0	15	1.30 ± 2.76
	14.0	15	9.43 ± 9.49
	12.5	15	23.15 ± 13.54

^aTemperature was weighted mean of 1 d. ^bIllumination time: 12.5 h, 0600-1830 h; 14.0 h, 0530-1930 h; 15.0 h, 0500-2000 h.

We developed a P/TGMS rice from a spontaneous male sterile segregant found in the F₂ population of cross 2490(indica)/Geng 3 (japonica)/MR365(indica).

To observe agronomic traits, outcrossing habits, and fertility alteration, Xin Guang S was sown every 10 d from 9 Apr to 4 Jul 1993 at Hangzhou and transplanted 30 d later at one plant/hill at 15 × 16.6 cm. Fertility was estimated by the seed set of bagged panicles. To identify photoperiod/temperature response, transplanted seedlings with five fully extended leaves were transferred into the phytotron at the China National Rice Research Institute (CNRRI) in 1992 and grown to ripening phase under different photoperiod/temperature settings.

Panicles of 15 plants were bagged at anthesis, and seed set was evaluated for each photoperiod/temperature treatment.

Growth duration of Xin Guang S from sowing to 20% heading varied from 80 to 102 d, depending on sowing date. Xin Guang S was about 85 cm tall with about 10 tillers/plant, white stigmas, and a 74.8% exertion rate.

Xin Guang S had complete and stable sterility with the typical abortion of pollen grains and no seed set before 25 Aug. After this time it exhibited high to partial sterility and then partial fertility from 15 to 25 Sep, during which time very few pollen grains were aborted, although seed set of bagged panicles was 16.1-25.1%.

In the phytotron, Xin Guang S showed complete sterility at high temperatures (30.1° C) regardless of daylength. At low temperatures (23.1-24.1° C), it showed high sterility under long daylength (14-15 h/d) and partial fertility under short daylength (12.5 h/d). Xin Guang S is therefore photoperiod-sensitive (see table).

Extensive testcrossing showed that hybrids had normal fertility when Xin Guang S was crossed with indica and japonica rice, suggesting that it is a potentially promising P/TGMS line for the two-line system of hybrid rice breeding. ■